

Qualitative Properties on Bulging Triangles and Their Original Triangles

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Abstract

We consider bulging triangles introduced by the author [5] and study their qualitative properties. We focus on the triangle consisting of edge-centers of a bulging triangle, “edge-central triangle.” In addition, we investigate the similarity to bulging triangles and centroids of their original triangles and edge-central triangles.

Keywords: Bulging Triangle, Acute-angled or Right-angled Original Triangle, Edge-radius, Edge-central Triangle, Its Centroid, Similarity of Bulging Triangle.

1. Introduction

Since bulging triangles, which are plane figures were introduced in [5], their mathematical properties have been studied; see [5, 6, 7].

The concept of bulging triangles is a generalization of that of Reuleaux triangles, and they are based on *acute-angled* triangles. They are characterized by the fact that they are convex figures. Indeed, obtuse-angled triangles cannot derive convex bulging triangles; see [5].

Reuleaux Triangle

Bulging Triangle

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In what follows, e.g., \overline{AB} and $|\overline{AB}|$ denote the segment and its length, respectively. Moreover, we write

$$a := |\overline{BC}|, \quad b := |\overline{CA}|, \quad c := |\overline{AB}|.$$

Bulging triangles are obtained by following these procedures:

- [1] Consider an acute-angled triangle $\triangle ABC$ such that $c > a > b$; by rotation and reflection, we can set this assumption without loss of generality.
- [2] Consider the perpendicular bisector ℓ_{AB} of \overline{AB} , and find the intersection point P of ℓ_{AB} and \overline{BC} . Note that P lies on \overline{BC} since $a > b$.
- [3] Draw the arc \widehat{AB} with P as the center and \overline{AP} , equivalently, \overline{BP} as the radius.
- [4] Consider the perpendicular bisector ℓ_{BC} of \overline{BC} , and find the intersection point Q of ℓ_{BC} and \overline{AB} . Note that Q lies on \overline{AB} since $c > b$.
- [5] Draw the arc \widehat{BC} with Q as the center and \overline{BQ} , equivalently, \overline{CQ} as the radius.
- [6] Consider the perpendicular bisector ℓ_{CA} of \overline{CA} , and find the intersection point R of ℓ_{CA} and \overline{AB} . Note that R lies on \overline{AB} since $c > a$.
- [7] Draw the arc \widehat{CA} with R as the center and \overline{AR} , equivalently, \overline{CR} as the radius.
- [8] The closed figure consisting of three arcs drawn according to the above procedure is called the **bulging triangle**, and is denoted by $\widehat{\triangle}ABC$.

The following terms are standard in the theory of bulging triangles.

Definition 1.1. [5, 6, 7] Let $\widehat{\triangle}ABC$ be a bulging triangle.

- 1) $\triangle ABC$ is called the **original triangle for** $\widehat{\triangle}ABC$.
- 2) The arcs \widehat{AB} , \widehat{BC} and \widehat{CA} are collectively called the **edges** of $\widehat{\triangle}ABC$, and are rewritten by \widetilde{AB} , \widetilde{BC} and \widetilde{CA} , respectively.
- 3) The points P , Q and R are called the **AB-center**, **BC-center** and **CA-center**, respectively. These are collectively referred to as the **edge-centers** of $\widehat{\triangle}ABC$.
- 4) $\angle APB$, $\angle BQC$ and $\angle CRA$ are called the **AB-central angle**, **BC-central angle** and **CA-central angle**, respectively. These three angles are collectively referred to as the **edge-central angles** of $\widehat{\triangle}ABC$.

It always holds that ℓ_{AB} , ℓ_{BC} and ℓ_{CA} intersect at one point, and it is the circumcenter of $\triangle ABC$.

To date, it has been found, e.g., that

Proposition 1.2. [7] For any acute-angled triangle $\triangle ABC$ such that $c > a > b$, P lies on the second longest side \overline{BC} and Q and R lie on the longest side \overline{AB} .

Proposition 1.3. [7] For $\widehat{\triangle}ABC$ such that $c > a > b$,

- 1) the AB-central angle $\angle APB$ is obtuse, right and acute if and only if the BC-central angle $\angle BQC$ is obtuse, right and acute, respectively;
- 2) the CA-center $\angle CRA$ is always acute.

Proposition 1.4. [7] Consider $\widehat{\triangle}ABC$ and write

$$P(a, b, c) := a^4 + b^4 + c^4 - 2a^2b^2 - 2b^2c^2. \tag{1.1}$$

Then, the following hold:

- i) $P(a, b, c) > 0$ if and only if $\max\{\angle APB, \angle BQC\} \geq \pi/2$ and $\angle CRA < \pi/2$. In particular, if $c \geq \sqrt{2}b$, then the right-hand-side claim holds.
- ii) $P(a, b, c) \leq 0$ if and only if $\max\{\angle APB, \angle BQC, \angle CRA\} < \pi/2$. However, all three edge-central angles are never right together.

Proposition 1.5. [7] Consider $\widehat{\triangle}ABC$, and let H_A, H_B and H_C be foets of perpendiculars from A to \overline{BC} , from B to \overline{CA} and from C to \overline{AB} , respectively. Then, edge-radii of $\widehat{\triangle}ABC$ are given by

$$r_{AB} = \frac{ca}{2|BH_C|}, \tag{1.2}$$

$$r_{BC} = \frac{ac}{2|BH_A|}, \tag{1.3}$$

$$r_{CA} = \frac{bc}{2|AH_B|}. \tag{1.4}$$

Theorem 1.6. [6, 5] Any bulging triangle is inscribed in the circumscribed circle of the original triangle for it. In other words, the circumscribed circle of $\widehat{\triangle}ABC$ coincides with that of $\triangle ABC$.

We often must discuss the “deep” and “intrinsic” qualitative properties of bulging triangles themselves and their original triangles, when studying bulging triangles. The aim of this paper is to investigate such properties.

2. Main Results and Their Proofs

Hereafter, P, Q and R stand for edge-centers of $\widehat{\Delta}ABC$. Moreover, when considering ΔABC and $\widehat{\Delta}ABC$, we always suppose that ΔABC is an *acute-angled triangle such that $c > a > b$* and $\widehat{\Delta}ABC$ is a bulging triangle from such ΔABC .

For convenience, we set the following new term in this paper.

Definition 2.1. We call ΔPQR the **edge-central triangle** of $\widehat{\Delta}ABC$.

2.1. Properties on Original Triangles for Bulging Triangles

Proposition 2.2. Let M be the midpoint of \overline{AB} . If $|\overline{BM}| < |\overline{CM}|$ (resp. $|\overline{BM}| > |\overline{CM}|$), then Q and R lie on \overline{AB} in the order of A, Q, M, R, B (resp. A, R, M, Q, B). Moreover, $|\overline{BM}| = |\overline{CM}|$ never holds. In other words, M always lies between Q and R.

Proof. Set $A(-\beta, 0)$, $B(\beta, 0)$ and $C(\alpha, \gamma)$ where $\alpha < 0$ and $\beta, \gamma > 0$. In this case, remark that M coincides with the origin O. It follows that

$$\alpha + \beta > 0, \quad \beta - \alpha > 0 \tag{2.1}$$

since $\alpha < 0$, $\beta > 0$ and $|\alpha| < |\beta|$; see the figure above. The straight line BC, $\ell(BC)$ is given by

$$y = \frac{-\gamma}{\beta - \alpha}(x - \beta) = \frac{-\gamma}{\beta - \alpha}x + \frac{\beta\gamma}{\beta - \alpha},$$

so we have

$$P\left(0, \frac{\beta\gamma}{\beta - \alpha}\right).$$

On the one hand, the perpendicular bisector ℓ_{BC} of \overline{BC} is given by

$$y = \frac{\beta - \alpha}{\gamma}\left(x - \frac{\alpha + \beta}{2}\right) + \frac{\gamma}{2} = \frac{\beta - \alpha}{\gamma}x + \frac{\alpha^2 - \beta^2 + \gamma^2}{2\gamma},$$

so we have

$$Q\left(-\frac{\alpha^2 - \beta^2 + \gamma^2}{2(\beta - \alpha)}, 0\right).$$

On the other hand, the perpendicular bisector ℓ_{CA} of \overline{CA} is given by

$$y = -\frac{\alpha + \beta}{\gamma}\left(x - \frac{\alpha - \beta}{2}\right) + \frac{\gamma}{2} = -\frac{\alpha + \beta}{\gamma}x + \frac{\alpha^2 - \beta^2 + \gamma^2}{2\gamma},$$

so we have

$$R\left(\frac{\alpha^2 - \beta^2 + \gamma^2}{2(\alpha + \beta)}, 0\right).$$

From equation (2.1), it follows that the x -coordinates of Q and R have opposite signs to each other. Note that $\alpha^2 - \beta^2 + \gamma^2 \neq 0$. Indeed, if $\alpha^2 - \beta^2 + \gamma^2 = 0$, then

$$|\overline{OA}| = |\overline{OB}| = |\overline{OC}|$$

since $\alpha^2 + \gamma^2 = |\overline{OC}|^2$ and $\beta^2 = |\overline{OA}|^2 = |\overline{OB}|^2$. Thus, O is the circumcenter of $\triangle ABC$, so $\angle ACB$ is right. This contradicts the assumption that $\triangle ABC$ is acute. Now, by virtue of the discussion above, we can conclude the desired claim. \square

Remark 2.3. We can immediately obtain $|\overline{BM}|$. Given the lengths of all sides of $\triangle ABC$, $|\overline{CM}|$ can be also easily obtained by the parallelogram law:

$$|\overline{BC}|^2 + |\overline{CA}|^2 = 2(|\overline{BM}|^2 + |\overline{CM}|^2).$$

Remark 2.4. The proof of Proposition 2.2 deduces that $\triangle PQR$ cannot be right or obtuse. By virtue of Proposition 2.2, the following is immediately derived.

Corollary 2.5. For any $\widehat{\triangle}ABC$, $\angle PQR$ and $\angle PRQ$ are always acute.

From these, we gain a sufficient condition for the edge-central triangle to be acute.

Theorem 2.6. If the AB-central angle $\angle APB$ is acute, then $\triangle PQR$ is acute.

Proof. Assume that $\angle APB$ is acute. Then, it is obviously that $\angle QPR$ is acute since $\angle QPR < \angle APB$. Hence, the claim immediately holds from this and Corollary 2.5. \square

Remark 2.7. If $\widehat{\triangle}ABC$ is a Reuleaux triangle, the edge-centers coincide with vertices, that is, P, Q and R coincide with C, A and B, respectively. Hence $\triangle PQR = \triangle ABC$, and so $\triangle PQR$ is acute and equilateral. Proposition 1.4 gives a paraphrase of Theorem 2.6 as follows.

Corollary 2.8. If $P(a, b, c) \leq 0$, $\triangle PQR$ is acute.

With this result, let us give a special term to equation (1.1).

Definition 2.9. We call $P(a, b, c)$ the **shape determinant** with respect to the original triangle for $\widehat{\triangle}ABC$.

2.2. Properties on the Sides of Edge-central Triangles

Proposition 2.10. For any $\widehat{\triangle}ABC$, one has

$$|\overline{QM}| < |\overline{RM}|. \tag{2.2}$$

Proof. Recall the setting of coordinates:

$$A(-\beta, 0), \quad B(\beta, 0), \quad C(\alpha, \gamma), \quad M(0, 0), \tag{2.3}$$

where $\alpha < 0$ and $\beta, \gamma > 0$. Then, we obtained the following information:

$$P \left(0, \frac{\beta\gamma}{\beta - \alpha} \right), \tag{2.4}$$

$$Q \left(-\frac{\alpha^2 - \beta^2 + \gamma^2}{2(\beta - \alpha)}, 0 \right), \tag{2.5}$$

$$R \left(\frac{\alpha^2 - \beta^2 + \gamma^2}{2(\alpha + \beta)}, 0 \right). \tag{2.6}$$

We therefore have

$$|\overline{QM}| = \frac{|\alpha^2 - \beta^2 - \gamma^2|}{2(\beta - \alpha)}, \tag{2.7}$$

$$|\overline{RM}| = \frac{|\alpha^2 - \beta^2 - \gamma^2|}{2(\alpha + \beta)}. \tag{2.8}$$

Now, since

$$\beta - \alpha > \alpha + \beta > 0,$$

we conclude equation (2.2) by comparing equation (2.7) with equation (2.8). □

Remark 2.11. According to Proposition 2.2, the points are arranged in the order A, Q, M, R, B, or A, R, M, Q, B. It is important for equation (2.2) to hold regardless of these arrangements.

We can gain the following claim as a corollary of Proposition 2.10.

Theorem 2.12. For any $\widehat{\triangle}ABC$, one has

$$|\overline{PQ}| < |\overline{PR}|.$$

Proof. The straight line PM is the perpendicular bisector of the straight line AB, that is, \overline{PM} is the height of $\triangle PQR$ when \overline{QR} is its base. Hence, this and equation (2.2) complete the proof. □

2.3. Properties on Edge-radii of Bulging Triangles

Theorem 2.13. For any $\widehat{\triangle}ABC$, one has

$$r_{AB} > r_{BC}.$$

In other words,

$$|\overline{BP}| > |\overline{BQ}|.$$

Proof. Consider $\triangle ABC$ and the foots of perpendiculars, H_A and H_C . Since

$$\angle ABH_A = \angle CBH_C \quad \text{and} \quad \angle AH_A B = \angle CH_C B = \frac{\pi}{2},$$

$\triangle ABH_A$ and $\triangle CBH_C$ are similar to each other. So

$$|\overline{AB}| : |\overline{BH_A}| = |\overline{BC}| : |\overline{BH_C}|,$$

and hence we have

$$\frac{a}{|\overline{BH_C}|} = \frac{c}{|\overline{BH_A}|}.$$

By virtue of Proposition 1.5 and $c > a$, we obtain the desired claim. □

Proposition 2.14. Let M be the midpoint of \overline{AB} . For $\widehat{\triangle}ABC$,

- 1) if $|\overline{BM}| < |\overline{CM}|$, then $r_{BC} < r_{CA}$;

2) if $|\overline{BM}| > |\overline{CM}|$, then $r_{BC} > r_{CA}$.

Proof. In case of 1), Proposition 2.2 implies that Q lies on \overline{AM} and R lies on \overline{BM} . If $\angle BQC$ is obtuse, then

$$r_{BC} = |\overline{CQ}| < |\overline{CR}| = r_{CA} \tag{2.9}$$

obviously holds. If $\angle BQC$ is acute, then equation (2.9) holds by Proposition 2.10. Hence, we obtain the desired claim. The case of 2) can be similarly proved. \square

Remark 2.15. From Proposition 2.14, r_{CA} is the smallest of the three edge-radii if $|\overline{BC}| > |\overline{CM}|$. It is however possible for r_{CA} to be the largest of them, that is, to satisfy $r_{CA} > r_{AB} > r_{BC}$ or $r_{AB} > r_{CA} > r_{BC}$ if $|\overline{BC}| < |\overline{CM}|$.

2.4. Centroids of Original Triangles and Edge-central Triangles

Theorem 2.16. Let G and G' be centroids of $\triangle ABC$ and $\triangle PQR$, respectively. H_* stands for the foot of the perpendicular of a vertex $*$ of $\triangle ABC$. M represents the midpoint of \overline{AB} . Then, their coordinates are given by

$$G \left(\frac{|\overline{MH}_C|}{3}, \frac{|\overline{CH}_C|}{3} \right), \tag{2.10}$$

$$G' \left(\frac{|\overline{MH}_C|(|\overline{BM}|^2 - |\overline{CM}|^2)}{3|\overline{AH}_C||\overline{BH}_C|}, \frac{|\overline{BM}||\overline{CH}_C|}{3|\overline{BH}_C|} \right). \tag{2.11}$$

In other words, G is transferred to G' by the linear transform

$$T = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{|\overline{BM}|^2 - |\overline{CM}|^2}{|\overline{AH}_C||\overline{BH}_C|} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{|\overline{BM}|}{|\overline{BH}_C|} \end{pmatrix}. \tag{2.12}$$

Proof. Recall the setting of the coordinates in the proof of Proposition 2.10. Set $G(x, y)$ and $G'(x', y')$. Recall the coordinates of edge-centers, equations (2.3), (2.4), (2.5) and (2.6). By these, we easily have

$$G \left(\frac{\alpha}{3}, \frac{\gamma}{3} \right),$$

$$G' \left(-\frac{\alpha(\alpha^2 - \beta^2 + \gamma^2)}{3(\beta + \alpha)(\beta - \alpha)}, \frac{\beta\gamma}{3(\beta - \alpha)} \right),$$

i.e.,

$$\begin{cases} x' = -\frac{\alpha^2 - \beta^2 + \gamma^2}{(\beta + \alpha)(\beta - \alpha)}x, \\ y' = \frac{\beta}{\beta - \alpha}y. \end{cases}$$

Since $\alpha = |\overline{MH}_C|$, $\gamma = |\overline{CH}_C|$, $\beta + \alpha = |\overline{AH}_C|$, $\beta - \alpha = |\overline{BH}_C|$, $\beta = |\overline{BM}|$ and

$$-(\alpha^2 - \beta^2 + \gamma^2) = \beta^2 - (\alpha^2 + \gamma^2) = |\overline{BM}|^2 - |\overline{CM}|^2,$$

we gain equations (2.10) and (2.11). Equation (2.12) is immediately obtained from the above simultaneous equations. \square

2.5. Similarity of Bulging Triangles

Definition 2.17 (e.g., [8]). Let \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} be figures.

- 1) (**Position of Similarity**) If there is a one-to-one correspondence between points on \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} , and the lines connecting the corresponding points all intersect at a point O , and they are all divided internally or externally by O to the same ratio, then \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} are said to be in a position of similarity.
- 2) (**Similarity and Congruence**) \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} are said to be similar to each other if one of the figures can be appropriately moved and placed in a position of similarity. Alternatively, \mathcal{A} is said to be similar to \mathcal{B} , if \mathcal{A} is enlarged or reduced around O to be able to coincide with \mathcal{B} . In particular, \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} which can be completely superimposed by movement are said to be congruent.

The same property as for a triangle holds for a bulging triangle as follows:

Theorem 2.18. Consider $\triangle ABC$. Take two points X and Y on \overline{AB} and \overline{AC} , respectively, so that \overline{XY} is parallel to \overline{BC} . Then,

$$|\widetilde{AB}| : |\widetilde{AC}| = |\widetilde{AX}| : |\widetilde{AY}|, \tag{2.13}$$

$$|\widetilde{BA}| : |\widetilde{BC}| = |\widetilde{XA}| : |\widetilde{XY}|, \tag{2.14}$$

$$|\widetilde{CB}| : |\widetilde{CA}| = |\widetilde{YX}| : |\widetilde{YA}| \tag{2.15}$$

hold between $\widehat{\triangle}ABC$ and $\widehat{\triangle}AXY$.

Proof. We prove only equation (2.13). Equations (2.14) and (2.15) can be proved in the same way. Without loss of generality, we can suppose that

$$|\overline{AB}| > |\overline{BC}| > |\overline{CA}|.$$

Take a point D (resp. Z) on \overline{BC} (resp. \overline{XY}) so that

$$|\overline{AD}| = |\overline{BD}| \quad (\text{resp. } |\overline{AZ}| = |\overline{XZ}|). \tag{2.16}$$

Put $r := |\overline{AD}| = |\overline{BD}|$ and $r' := |\overline{AZ}| = |\overline{XZ}|$. In other words, D and Z are the AB -center of $\widehat{\triangle}ABC$ and AX -center of $\widehat{\triangle}AXY$, respectively. Moreover, r and r' are the AB -radius of $\widehat{\triangle}ABC$ and AX -radius of $\widehat{\triangle}AXY$, respectively. Z obviously lies on \overline{AD} , since $\triangle AXY$ is a reduced figure of $\triangle ABC$. So we have $\angle ADB = \angle AZX$. This fact and equation (2.16) imply that $\triangle ABD$ and $\triangle AXZ$ are similar to each other. Therefore we obtain

$$r' = \frac{|\overline{AX}|}{|\overline{AB}|}r. \tag{2.17}$$

Likewise, take the AC -center E and AY -center W on \overline{BC} and \overline{XY} , respectively, and denote by ρ and ρ' the AC -radius and AY -radius, respectively. Note that $\angle AEC = \angle AWY$. Then, we have

$$\rho' = \frac{|\overline{AY}|}{|\overline{AC}|}\rho. \tag{2.18}$$

Putting

$$\theta := \angle ADB = \angle AZX, \quad \phi := \angle AEC = \angle AWY,$$

we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\widetilde{AB}| : |\widetilde{AC}| &= r\theta : \rho\phi, \\ |\widetilde{AX}| : |\widetilde{AY}| &= r'\theta : \rho'\phi. \end{aligned}$$

Equations (2.17) and (2.18) imply that

$$|\widetilde{AX}| : |\widetilde{AY}| = \frac{|\overline{AX}|}{|\overline{AB}|} r\theta : \frac{|\overline{AY}|}{|\overline{AC}|} \rho\phi.$$

Since $\triangle ABC$ and $\triangle AXY$ are obviously similar to each other, it holds that

$$\frac{|\overline{AX}|}{|\overline{AB}|} = \frac{|\overline{AY}|}{|\overline{AC}|}.$$

Hence, we obtain

$$|\widetilde{AX}| : |\widetilde{AY}| = r\theta : \rho\phi = |\widetilde{AB}| : |\widetilde{AC}|.$$

This completes the proof. □

Remark 2.19. Theorem 2.18 implies that

$$|\widetilde{AX}| : |\widetilde{AB}| = |\widetilde{XY}| : |\widetilde{BC}| = |\widetilde{YA}| : |\widetilde{CA}|,$$

so we deduce that $\widehat{\triangle} AXY$ and $\widehat{\triangle} ABC$ are similar to each other. It is of course true that if $\widehat{\triangle} AXY$ and $\widehat{\triangle} ABC$ are similar to each other, then equations (2.13)-(2.15) hold.

From Remark 2.19, we can paraphrase the claim of Theorem 2.18 as follows.

Corollary 2.20. Consider two triangles $\triangle ABC$ and $\triangle AXY$ which are similar to each other. Then, $\widehat{\triangle} ABC$ and $\widehat{\triangle} AXY$ are also similar to each other, and they satisfy equations (2.13)-(2.15).

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